

The MixoExplorer Manual

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MixoExplorer mixoplankton simulator - QUICK START

Install Powersim 10 Studio Cockpit and load model

- The *Powersim Studio 10 Cockpit* application works only on PCs operating *Microsoft Windows*.
- Visit the *Powersim Studio* download site at <https://powersim.com/download-cockpit/>
- Download *Cockpit* (64-bit or 32-bit; most PCs will be 64-bit).
- Follow instructions provided by *Powersim* to install the software. (Accept default suggestions.)
- Download the MixoExplorer model from <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19826770>
- To run the MixoExplorer model, locate the file in your *MS Windows* file directory using *Explorer*.
- The file should have the *Powersim Studio 10* logo associated with it - clicking on the file name will open the file within the application.
- The model will open into a Home page; just following the onscreen instructions.

From the MixoExplorer Home page, select **Description** and investigate options and explanations.

From the *Description* page, select **Explore** to enter the page to operate the simulator itself.

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1. Introduction

MixoExplorer is a simulation model that enables exploration of the impact of environmental conditions on a marine plankton food web under the traditional (phytoplankton-zooplankton) versus new (including mixoplankton) paradigm of marine ecology.

The traditional paradigm describes interactions between phytoplankton ('producers') that are photosynthetic (using light and inorganic nutrients, such as nitrate and ammonium) and the zooplankton ('consumers') that predate upon them. Mixoplankton are organisms that perform both photosynthesis and predation; they are thus both producers and consumers. For more information, visit www.mixotroph.org.

Mixoplankton and a new paradigm for ecology in coastal and marine waters

Briefing on how mixoplankton affect ocean health, fish and aquaculture

Read more about marine 'killer triffids'

Importance of mixoplankton paradigm in the United Nations Plankton Manifesto

Mitra, A. and Cox, N. (2026) *Mixoplankton and a new paradigm for ecology in coastal and marine waters*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18387815>

MixoExplorer provides a platform to examine the consequences of including alternative types of mixoplankton – non-constitutive mixoplankton and constitutive mixoplankton.

Non-Constitutive Mixoplankton (NCM) has no innate capacity to perform photosynthesis; it acquires that capability by repurposing chloroplasts it has stolen from its prey. **Constitutive mixoplankton** (CM) has the capability to make and maintain its own chloroplasts, in the same way that phytoplankton do.

MixoExplorer operates via a Windows OS application, *Powersim Studio 10 Cockpit*, which is available as a free download for installation on your PC.

2. Installing Powersim Studio 10 Cockpit and opening MixoExplorer

IMPORTANT

If you already have any other *Powersim Studio 10* product installed, do NOT install *Cockpit*!

Doing so will overwrite your existing product. Your existing product should open a project that has been saved for use by *Cockpit*, as has **MixoExplorer**.

You will need administration rights to your PC to perform the installation, which is a once-only requirement.

The simulator is operated with a Windows PC application, **Powersim Cockpit**.

Cockpit is a free-to-end-user application that enables the user to run model projects that have been developed using Powersim Studio Premium.

Cockpit only works on the MS Windows OS.

Note that this modelling software makes intensive demands of your PC's CPU. Depending on the power of your PC, modelling can affect (slow) the operation of other applications that you may be running, and vice versa.

The shortest run time will be obtained using a PC with multiple cores (i7 and upwards) and having more and faster RAM. Good graphic capabilities are also beneficial.

To download *Cockpit*, visit <https://powersim.com/download-cockpit/> and follow the Quick Start guide on page 2 of this manual to install this software.

Opening a project

It is easiest to locate simulation model via Windows explorer, and just double click on it.

A file recognised by the *Powersim Studio 10* Cockpit application will be indicated by the *Powersim Studio* logo, as in this example:

The *Studio 10* file extension is .sip.

Opening the .sip file will open up the simulator at its Home page. Other pages are available by appropriate buttons.

For example:

Common to all project pages, there are buttons to operate the simulation at the top-left of the window. Included here is 'Zoom percentage', which provides an option to optimize the 'Fit' for that project page to the user's screen.

3. Description of the MixoExplorer code

MixoExplorer is presented as a user product; you cannot see or edit that actual model itself.

However, **MixoExplorer** was developed from the MixoEdu model, full details of which is available via:

A Simple N-based Mixoplankton Model

Kevin John Flynn and Aditee Mitra (2021)

Published by Zenodo, doi: 10.5281/zenodo.5040445

<https://zenodo.org/records/5040445>

This publication provides a comprehensive description of core features of the model.

4. Operating MixoExplorer

On entering each page, selecting 'Fit' from the 'Zoom Percentage' drop down (ribbon menu, top left) will show the entire page on one screen.

Home page

The model opens into the *Home* page.

Switch into the *Description* page using the button on the left.

Description page

Select 'Fit' from the viewing magnification option in the ribbon.

KEY for processes in schematic and in the table

- (i) photosynthesis
- (ii) predation
- (iii) ammonium uptake (to support photosynthesis)
- (iv) nitrate uptake to support photosynthesis
- (v) release (excretion) of ammonium

Click here for details on each process

PROTIST Type	i	ii	iii	iv	v
Zooplankton	x	✓	x	x	✓
NCM	✓	✓	✓	x	✓
CM	✓	✓	✓	✓*	✓
Phytoplankton	✓	x	✓	✓*	x

This schematic shows how the nutrients, ammonium and nitrate, are used by different plankton types, how those organisms interact, and then how the nutrient is recycled.

Each of the organism types have different physiological features, as indicated in the numbered 'Key'. Find out more about those features and the organisms themselves by clicking in the indicated buttons.

Click in the information '!' buttons for additional insight.

This page provides an annotated schematic of the food web described by the model.

The simulation is of events in the euphotic zone, separated from the deeper darker waters by a barrier called a **thermocline**. There is an exchange of nutrients and a loss of plankton into and out of the euphotic zone, indicated by the vertical dark blue arrows in the schematic. Oceanic water tends to have a deeper mixed layer depth, clearer water and less nutrient than do coastal waters. These features all affect the availability of light required to drive photosynthesis:

- a deeper mixed layer depth takes plankton into deeper darker water
- clearer water allows light to penetrate deeper; water near the land contains coloured materials (tannins) from the land, as well as suspended materials (clay, sand)
- more nutrients enable more microalgae to grow, which decreases light penetration; this effect is decreased through consumption of microalgae by the predators.

In the plankton component, the most important thing to appreciate is that you can configure the 'Protist' to represent one of 4 different types of organism. These have different physiologies, as indicated in the table and the schematic.

The traditional description of marine plankton assumes the presence of only producers (a type of microalgae called **phytoplankton**) and consumers (called **zooplankton**).

Phytoplankton are a type of microalgae that use sunlight to support photosynthesis and use nutrients such as ammonium and nitrate. Important types of phytoplankton include the prokaryote cyanobacteria, and the protist diatoms. **Zooplankton** (which includes the single celled protist zooplankton and metazoan animals such as copepods and krill), eat phytoplankton and other zooplankton (note the curved arrow out and then back into the Zooplankton box in the schematic). During digestion of their prey, zooplankton release (excrete) ammonium; this then becomes available for the microalgae to use, continuing the nutrient cycle.

There are by default already such organisms in the model, labelled in the schematic as 'Phytoplankton' and 'Zooplankton'. When configuring the 'Protist' to continue the traditional description, you will need to set the 'Protist' as either '**phytoplankton**' or '**zooplankton**'; this would add an additional producer or an additional consumer. Note from the schematic which of the nutrient flows (indicated by arrows) would then operate!

Science now recognises that many protist microalgae that used to be labelled as 'phytoplankton' can also eat. These organisms are called **mixoplankton**.

Mixoplankton are protist microalgae that use sunlight for photosynthesis, with consumption of ammonium and perhaps also nitrate, and also consume food. Mixoplankton are thus producers and consumers in the same organism.

There are two mixoplankton types described in the model:

(1) NCM – these are **non-constitutive mixoplankton**. These organisms lack a constitutive (built-in) ability to make chloroplasts. NCM thus have to acquire the ability to photosynthesize by eating a microalgae and stealing their chloroplasts. In the type of NCM described here those chloroplasts only last for a few days, so they need to keep eating the occasional microalgae prey (either a phytoplankton, or another mixoplankton). Note also from the schematic that the NCM cannot use nitrate; they can only use ammonium.

Technically, the type of NCM described in *MixoExplorer* is a generalist (GNCM), which can use chloroplasts from various microalgae prey. There is another type of non-constitutive

mixoplankton, a specialist version (SNCM) which is much better at looking after the chloroplasts that it steals; SNCM only need to steal chloroplasts every several weeks, but they can only do so from a specific prey type.

(2) CM – these are **constitutive mixoplankton**. These organisms, just like the phytoplankton, possess a constitutive (built-in) ability to make chloroplasts. Unlike the NCM, typically they can use nitrate, although there are some exceptions.

Note that while mixoplankton may release ammonium, zooplankton always release ammonium. The reason for the difference is that the mixoplankton can immediately re-assimilate ammonium released during prey digestion using energy and carbon metabolites gained from photosynthesis. This is especially important in low-nutrient conditions.

To obtain more information on each aspect shown in the schematic, click the information buttons . There are additional buttons that will take you to other pages.

Clicking the 'grey' button within the KEY ...

KEY for processes in schematic and in the table

- (i) photosynthesis
- (ii) predation
- (iii) ammonium uptake (to support photosynthesis)
- (iv) nitrate uptake to support photosynthesis
- (v) release (excretion) of ammonium

Click here for details on each process

... will take you to the following page:

PHYSIOLOGICAL DETAILS

- PHOTOSYNTHESIS:** uses energy from light and CO₂ to make sugars. Together with dissolved inorganic nitrogen (**DIN** as ammonium and nitrate), this leads to **production** of biomass. Light availability varies with day-length, water depth and water clarity. Depth, clarity, and the amount of biomass affect light availability.
- PREDATION:** this **consumes** prey biomass. Consumed prey is digested with a portion converted into predator biomass and the undigested portion voided as faeces. 30% of the digested material is excreted as CO₂ and other inorganic nutrients (e.g., ammonium).
- AMMONIUM (NH₄⁺) UPTAKE:** this is the preferred DIN for photosynthetic organisms to acquire nitrogen (N) to make proteins, RNA, DNA. Ammonium is also the major type of N released by consumers, such as during predator-prey interactions. This ammonium can be immediately recycled back into production flowing uptake by photosynthetic organisms.
- NITRATE (NO₃⁻) UPTAKE:** in absence of sufficient ammonium, photosynthetic organisms may use nitrate as their DIN source. This is especially important early in the season (springtime), as nitrate produced by nitrification (a process converting ammonium into nitrate) has accumulated in surface waters over the winter months. As the season develops, the nitrate is consumed and ammonium is produced by predator-prey interactions; this ammonium supports summer plankton growth in surface waters.
- RELEASE (EXCRETION) OF AMMONIUM:** the recycling of ammonium occurs because the N in biomass is coupled to C; this is most obvious in proteins. When organisms grow, they consume some of the C from their food, converting it to CO₂. In so doing they produce an excess of N which they must remove; they do so by excreting it as ammonium.

What is special about mixoplankton physiology

- PRODUCERS:** These are photosynthetic organisms that use CO₂ and ammonium (NH₄⁺) to make biomass.
- CONSUMERS (predators):** These use biomass originally created by producers but in doing so inefficiencies result in the loss of a portion (at least 30%) of their food as CO₂ (respiration) and NH₄⁺ (excretion). The inefficiency is termed Specific Dynamic Action (SDA).
- MIXOPLANKTON** are both **producers and consumers**. Mixoplankton benefit by internally recycling waste C and N from their consumer activity to directly support their producer activity. In essence, mixoplankton are not subjected to SDA.

Phytoplankton: Photosynthetic producer uses light, CO₂ and dissolved inorganic nitrogen (nitrate, NO₃⁻ or ammonium, NH₄⁺) to make biomass for growth.

Zooplankton: Predator eats food; a proportion is voided as organic matter (faeces); an additional proportion (ca. 30%) is lost during assimilation of the consumed biomass as new biomass for growth. This loss (Specific Dynamic Action, SDA) is as CO₂ and ammonium (NH₄⁺).

Mixoplankton: Mixoplankton couple production and consumption by internally recycling CO₂ and NH₄⁺ produced by SDA (during digestion of prey) back to directly support additional production via photosynthesis.

This page describes, in some detail, the physiology of the organisms so that you may better appreciate the schematic on the *Description* page.

Return to the *Description* page when done.

A key feature of the simulator is that the **Protist** organism (in the centre of the schematic) may be configured as any one of four different organism types. The physiologies of these types are summarised in this table:

PROTIST Type	i	ii	iii	iv	v
Zooplankton	x	✓	x	x	✓
NCM	✓	✓	✓	x	✓
CM	✓	✓	✓	✓*	✓
Phytoplankton	✓	x	✓	✓*	x

Clicking on the information buttons gives more information. Clicking on the names themselves will take you to the following pages:

Select 'Fit' from the viewing magnification option in the ribbon.

PROTIST ZOOPLANKTON

- Eukaryote (i.e., protist) predators.
- Usually single-cell organisms. Sizes range from 3-1000 μm (0.003-1.0 mm).
- Usually motile though some use pseudopodia and mucus webs to draw prey in.
- Life cycle duration of 1 or a few days.
- Phagotrophic (i.e., engulfing) **consumers** that grow by capturing and eating other plankton or detritus, often displaying significant selectivity.
- They can also use dissolved organic nutrients ('osmotrophy'; not considered here).
- Cannot photosynthesize (no phototrophy).

METAZOAN ZOOPLANKTON

- Multicellular (i.e., animal) predators.
- Sizes range from ca. 0.5 mm to 0.5 m.
- Typically, highly motile, with some capable of extensive migration, vertically in the water column.
- Multiple life-stages from egg through juveniles to adults, and relatively long life cycles
- Raptorial or filter feeding on other plankton or detritus, often displaying significant selectivity.
- No osmotrophy; no phototrophy.

Select 'Fit' from the viewing magnification option in the ribbon.

NON-CONSTITUTIVE MIXOPLANKTON (NCM)

- Eukaryote (i.e., protist) producers+consumers.
- Single-cell organisms. Sizes range from 50-1000 μm (0.05-1.0 mm).
- Usually motile though some use pseudopodia and mucus webs to draw prey in.
- Life cycle duration of 1 day or a few days.
- Phagotrophic, like **protist zooplankton**.
- Phototrophic, partly like protist phytoplankton but their **ability to photosynthesize is acquired** ('stolen') from their phytoplankton prey (i.e., it is not constitutive). Stolen chloroplasts are not maintained and **must be replaced frequently**. Ability to use external nutrients may be poor; nutrients for phototrophy mainly sourced by internal recycling from feeding wastes.
- They can also use dissolved organic nutrients ('osmotrophy'; not considered here) and are thus **photo-osmo-phago-mixotrophs**.

Powersim Simulation Presentation

95%

Select 'Fit' from the viewing magnification option in the ribbon.

ARKdynamics.org

CONSTITUTIVE MIXOPLANKTON (CM)

- Eukaryote (i.e., protist) producers+consumers.
- Single-cell organisms. Sizes range from 5-1000 μm (0.05-1.0 mm).
- Usually motile though some use pseudopodia and mucus webs to draw prey in.
- Life cycle duration of 1 or a few days.
- Phagotrophic, like **protist zooplankton**.
- Phototrophic, like **protist phytoplankton**, with an inherent (constitutive) ability to photosynthesise, synthesising and maintaining chloroplasts (*compare with NCM*).
- They can also use dissolved organic nutrients ('osmotrophy'; not considered here) and are thus **photo-osmo-phago-mixotrophs**.

Return to Description

400.00000

Powersim Simulation Presentation

95%

Select 'Fit' from the viewing magnification option in the ribbon.

ARKdynamics.org

PHYTOPLANKTON

- Prokaryote and eukaryote (i.e., protist) microalgae.
- Single-cell organisms, though many grow in chains or clumps. Sizes range from 1-200 μm (0.001-0.2 mm).
- Some are motile or can regulate their buoyancy.
- Life cycle duration of 1 day or a few days.
- Photosynthetic **producers** that grow using light, CO_2 and dissolved inorganic nutrients.
- They can also use dissolved organic nutrients ('osmotrophy'; not considered here) and are thus **photo-osmo-mixotrophs**.
- They cannot eat (no phagotrophy).

Return to Description

400.00000

In each instance, click 'Return to the Description' to get back to the Description page when done. When you are ready, from the Description page, click to enter the Explore page.

Explore page

From this page, you configure the model and run the simulations.

You can return to the other pages at any time.

The screenshot shows the ARKdynamics.org simulation interface. On the left, there are navigation buttons for Home, Description, and Explore. The main area contains several configuration panels:

- Protist Type:** Radio buttons for 1. Zooplankton, 2. NCM, 3. CM, and 4. Phytoplankton.
- Using Nitrate:** Radio buttons for NO and YES.
- Nitrate (NO3):** Radio buttons for low, medium, and high.
- Ammonium (NH4):** Radio buttons for low, medium, and high.
- Mixed Layer Depth:** Radio buttons for Ocean and Coast.
- Water clarity:** Radio buttons for Ocean and Coast.
- Light:Day fraction:** Radio buttons for 0.50, 0.70, and 1.00.

 On the right, there are three graphs:

- CONFIGURATIONS:** A step function graph showing the value of 'Type' (solid red line) and 'NO3 use' (dashed black line) over time (0 to 400 days).
- Nutrients:** A line graph showing the concentration of Nitrate (NO3, cyan line) and Ammonium (NH4, blue line) in ug N L⁻¹ over time.
- Biomass:** A line graph showing the biomass of Phytoplankton (green line), Protist (black line), and Zooplankton (red line) in ug N L⁻¹ over time.

 Additional elements include an INSTRUCTIONS panel with keyboard shortcuts (Ctrl+R, Ctrl+Space) and a note that F9 rescales plots. A 'Select 'Fit'' callout points to a magnification button in the ribbon.

It is recommended that you check each of the information buttons before continuing.

Before commencing any scientific study, you should make a plan so that you approach the exercise in a logical fashion. There are many options available to you here, so it would be easy to become confused in making a summary of the results.

Ideally you would devise this plan set around a series of hypotheses.

A hypothesis is a formal statement such as:

H₀ Setting the protist plankton type as an NCM rather than as a CM will not alter the outcome of the simulation. This is the ‘null hypothesis’; by convention this states that we expect nothing to happen.

H₁ Setting the protist plankton type as an NCM rather than as a CM will alter the outcome of the simulation. This alternative hypothesis (or hypotheses) present suggestions of what may happen.

Once you are ready:

- reset the model using Ctrl+R (which will clear the graphs and reset the time that is indicated in the bottom right-hand corner) to zero days.
- Configure the model as required.
- Start the simulation using Ctrl+space. Note that this acts as a toggle; if you repeat this action, it will alternately pause and un-pause.
- The simulation will automatically pause every 100 days. At this point you could alter the conditions if you so wish.

Note that changes you make to the physiology of the protist plankton are recorded in the 'CONFIGURATIONS' plot. The information button in this plot draws your attention to the following:

IMPORTANT NOTE

The simulation pauses every 100d, at which point you can change the type of organism represented by **Protist**. *This, of course, could never happen in reality!*

However, making such changes does allow you to explore what might happen if a different type of protist entered an ecosystem, whether a particular configuration might be of benefit or not.

Real world introductions of different species may occur in response to changes in water conditions (such as temperature, salinity, turbulence), the emergence of encysted organisms (various protist plankton have resting stages, cysts, which excyst under certain conditions), or alien introductions (for example from the emptying of ship ballast water which contained cysts of different plankton).

Like all science, results from studies on a particular system can only indicate what may happen, what may be true; they cannot give you 100% confidence. As you study more systems, obtaining similar results, your confidence in understanding reality will improve.

5. Things to try

There are many experiments that you could conduct but the following might provide some stimulus.

- Under oceanic conditions of low nutrients and mixing depths, which configurations do best?
- How does preventing the protist CM or phytoplankton from using nitrate affect what happens?
- If fisheries production is related to the success of the larger zooplankton, what configurations of 'Protist' may be beneficial for supporting fisheries under different conditions?

- What conditions are conducive to rapidly establishing what are termed 'steady-state' conditions? These are when the biomass and nutrient plots do not exhibit strong oscillations; oscillations are caused by predator-prey 'mismatch'.

There are other aspects that you may wish to consider that are not simulated here:

- What might be the consequence under different conditions if the mixoplankton were noxious? Most marine harmful algal bloom (HAB) species are mixoplankton*.
- Bacteria are not represented here. In coastal waters, where light penetration is low thus hindering photosynthesis, bacterial growth is high and many mixoplankton can eat bacteria.
- Many mixoplankton eat other mixoplankton. How do you think this interaction might play out? How could you modify the model schematic to explore this?

*Mitra A, Flynn, KJ (2021). HABs & the Mixoplankton Paradigm. *Harmful Algae News*. 67: 4-6
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5109703>

6. An Evolutionary Perspective

In evolution, mixoplankton represent an intermediate between protist zooplankton and protist phytoplankton!

Mixoplankton evolved from ancient protist zooplankton by gaining an ability to photosynthesize. The earliest mixoplankton acquired photosynthesis by not immediately digesting their cyanobacterial prey but exploiting the sugars those ingested prey continued to synthesize when inside the protist; it is no coincidence that a cyanobacteria resembles the chloroplast in a eukaryote phototroph. This type of mixoplankton would have been similar to what we now term, a non-constitutive mixoplankton (NCM), because they lack a constitutive (built-in) capability to photosynthesize. Later evolution of such organisms resulted in the ability to replicate and control chloroplasts becoming a constitutive part of the protist cell; these organisms would have been similar in their physiology to what we now term, a constitutive mixoplankton (CM). That transition would also have seen the evolution of the ability to use other nutrients (such as nitrate) rather than just internally recycling nutrients from prey digestion. The protist phytoplankton then evolved from ancient CM through the loss of the ability to eat; they became completely reliant on their constitutive capability to perform photosynthesis.

Why some CM lost the ability to eat, thus becoming phytoplankton, is unknown. However, CM species grown in the laboratory in conditions without food, lose their ability to feed after many months. It seems plausible, then, that protist phytoplankton evolved in what we call immature ecosystems, which are dominated by inorganic nutrients (which would support photosynthesis) and contain few other organisms (and hence few prey organisms).

If you want to consider such a series of evolutionary** transitions using the model, you need to run the simulation with the protist configured in the following order: zooplankton, NCM, CM, phytoplankton.

**Mitra A, Flynn KJ, Stoecker DK, Raven JA (2024). Trait trade-offs in phagotrophic microalgae: the mixoplankton conundrum. *European Journal of Phycology*, 59:51. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09670262.2023.2216259>